

DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Improving the socio-economic status of women in our country, increasing their entrepreneurial activity, providing vocational training and employment, further increasing the role of businesswomen in the development of the economy. Human capital, human rights, gender equality and sustainable development are a chain of interrelated issues that are relevant today. Gender equality is important in itself; it is manifested in the role of women in the development of society and the strong influence of human potential on labor productivity. This article analyzes the issues related to the improvement of the women's labor market, the continuation of the policy of increasing the socio-economic activity of women, and based on these analyzes, conclusions and proposals are formed.*

Keywords: *human capital, labor market, gender equality, economy, society, professional education, human rights, quality of life.*

Introduction. Our wise people have always respected women, living with high respect for women has become an age-old value of our country. This is also confirmed by the fact that one of the largest chapters of the Holy Qur'an is called "Nisa", that is, "Women". In this Surah, Allah calls men to treat women fairly.

In the holy hadith, women are also commanded to always do good. Imam Bukhari, Imam Moturidi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Amir Timur, Alisher Navoi, Babur Mirza, our great ancestors and our enlightened ancestors also taught about the role and importance of women in the peaceful, strong and prosperous family and in the education of children. who emphasized that the secret is incomparable?

Today, women are working selflessly in the process of change and renewal in our society, in the management system, in the fields of entrepreneurship, science, health care, culture and art, and in neighborhoods. (Mirziyoev, 2022).

Thanks to the high economic growth rates achieved in recent years, Uzbekistan has made some progress in reducing gender inequality. At the same time, there are a number of demographic and structural problems, one of which is the insufficient efficiency of involving women in economic activities.

The reforms carried out in the field have a positive effect on the place of our country in international rankings, and in the Women, Business and Law Index of the World Bank, Uzbekistan is among the 27 countries that have implemented significant reforms in terms of women's rights and gender equality in 2020. ranked 134th out of 190 countries, rising 5 places
Uzbekistan has always shown that it is committed to the goals and principles of the UN Charter and other universally recognized norms of international law.
Gender equality is both a development goal and a sound approach to economic policy, as development is seen as a process of expanding freedoms for everyone, women and men equally.

The socio-economic policy carried out in Uzbekistan at all stages of reforms includes wide-ranging issues. Additional guarantees were given regarding the systematic increase of the population's income, the formation of employment and labor relations, the social protection and support of certain categories of the population, including women entrepreneurs and farmers.

In particular, in order to ensure the employment of women, to widely involve them in business activities, the practice of allocating preferential loans was launched. More than 30% of the clients of the microcredit base of commercial banks are women. Loans in the amount of 4.9 trillion soums were allocated to more than 172 thousand women at the expense of commercial banks. As a result, the number of women who started business increased by 45,000 in one year. Starting from 2019, a system of providing employment to the population and creating new jobs on the basis of the state order was established. The procedure for issuing temporary work permits to self-employed citizens and recording their work experience has been introduced. As a result, the share of women employed in the informal sector reached 27%.

Special attention was also paid to the development of remote areas of the republic, beautification of villages, and reduction of poverty by supporting the economic activity of women living in villages. More than 1.5 million women work in various fields of agriculture. 20% of business entities, including 7.3% of farms, are headed by women. Media activities are also important in promoting and achieving gender equality. The number of radio broadcasts and television shows that reflect the image of modern socially and politically active women and highlight the opportunities created for women and men has increased.

In order to organize systematic work on the consistent implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations Global Agenda, the national goals and tasks of Uzbekistan in the field of sustainable development until 2030 have been adopted in our country. In order to ensure gender equality and expand the rights and opportunities of all women, necessary measures have been determined in the political, social, economic and other spheres.

In 2003, Professor Pan Jinxi (2003) first proposed the concept of gender human capital. After that, research on women's human capital began. Although high rates of modernization in various sectors of the economy are driving growth and development, they can also leave women behind because they lack the skills and education necessary to successfully adapt to rapid structural changes. Currently, women make up about 50 percent of the country's population, but their participation in the formal labor market remains limited.

Human capital development is hard work. Therefore, it cannot be done in one day. There are no ready-made solutions in this regard. Each country should determine its own direction. From this point of view, a mechanism of targeted work for young people and women is being introduced in Uzbekistan today. Despite the fact that the gender gap has been reduced due to the serious efforts of the government, the problems of gender inequality in the development of some areas have remained. A number of sectors are characterized by significant differences in average income level by gender, there are problems in increasing the number of women in the labor market.

Analysis of literature on the topic Relying on foreign experiences, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of entrepreneurship and business and their practical application. Among them, we can include famous scientists such as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of entrepreneurship in the economy, while the researches conducted in

the field of marketing in our country for many years are based on national characteristics. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, R. Boltaboev, Sh.D. Ergashkhodjaeva Sh.A. Musayeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Women, Business and the Law 2023 details the current state of women's legal rights. This study presents a compilation of data and an index of women's working life. Governments, the private sector and civil society can use this framework to identify and remove barriers to women's economic empowerment and to encourage participation in the workforce and entrepreneurship.

The World Bank Group's lending and technical assistance operations use data on women, business, and law to provide an analytical framework for project development. Other institutions, such as the Atlantic Council; equal measures 2030 agenda; Georgetown Institute for Women, Peace and Security; inheritance fund; Millennium Challenges Corporation; and UN Women use it to promote the status of women in society. Women's economic activity is lower than men's in the whole world and in Uzbekistan. According to the results of 2021, this figure was 41.3% among women and 56.9% among men.¹

StatisticsAccording to the data, by the beginning of 2021, the working-age population was 20,135,100, of which 9,629,800 were women. In 2021, the unemployment rate among women was 13.3% (compared to 6.1% in the world). This is twice the unemployment rate among men. The majority of unemployed women are women with secondary (65.8 percent) and secondary (28.5 percent) education, as well as women with higher education (3.4 percent).

Table 1 shows the share of women in the total number of jobs in our country by type of economic activity. As can be seen in this table, the lowest percentage of women in jobs according to the type of economic activity is observed in the economic activity of construction, transportation and storage, according to the indicators of 2021, construction activity is 6.3% and transportation activity is 7.1%. is organizing According to the type of economic activity, the highest indicator was observed in educational activity 73.8%, health care and social services 77.3%.

In 2022, the labor market participation rate of the able-bodied population was 60%, while this indicator was 71.9% among men and 46.6% among women. In general, the economic activity of women is 1.5% less than the economic activity of men.

The share of women in total employment by type of economic activity in 2016-2021, %²

Indicators	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Rural forestry and fisheries	43.7	44.3	43.1	43.2	42.4	42.4
manufacturing industry	47.1	47.6	45.2	47.0	46.2	45.8
construction	5.8	5.8	5.8	6.2	6.3	6.3
wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	51.5	51.8	50.3	51.5	49.7	49.0
Transport and storage	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.1

¹The official website of the World Bank. Electronic source:

<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/b60c615b09e7-46e4-84c1-bd5f4ab88903/content>

²Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Electronic source: www.gender.stat.uz

accommodation and food services	52.4	52.8	51.7	52.1	51.7	51.0
information and communication	32.7	32.7	34.4	32.3	35.2	35.0
financial and insurance activities	37.3	38.2	38.7	34.8	37.4	37.6
public administration and defense; compulsory social security	29.1	29.4	28.4	26.8	27.8	27.5
provision of health and social services	76.5	76.6	76.5	76.8	76.3	77.3
Education	75.6	75.6	75.7	75.7	74.9	73.8

According to UNESCO, only 30 percent of researchers in the world are women. As more women enter universities, many are forgoing the higher education necessary for a career in science. In addition, there are stereotypes that girls face, the responsibilities of caring for the family, and the prejudices that women may face when choosing a career. In previous years, there were certain differences in the percentage of students studying in higher education institutions by gender (Table 2).

2016-2022 percentage of students studying in higher education institutions by gender, % per academic year³

Indicators	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022
<i>total</i>	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Women	38.2	40.0	44.3	45.9	45.5	45.6
Men	61.8	60.0	55.7	54.1	54.5	54.4
Undergraduate	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Women	38.3	40.1	44.4	46.1	45.6	45.6
Men	61.7	59.9	55.6	53.9	54.4	45.4
Master's	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Women	36.8	38.0	40.5	41.6	42.7	47.0
Men	63.2	62.0	59.5	58.4	57.3	53.0

We can see from the above table that in 2016-2017, 38.3% of women studied in higher education institutions in the field of undergraduate education. we can see that in men, this figure is 61.7%, which is 33.4% more than in women. By the beginning of the 2021-2022 academic year, the number of women studying at the bachelor's level made up 45.6%, which increased by 7.3% compared to the 2016-2017 academic year. In 2021-2022, 54.4% of men studying at higher education institutions are 8.8% more than women studying at higher education institutions. we can see that it happened.

In 2016-2017, 36.8% of women studied in the field of master's education of higher education organizations. in men, this figure was 63.2%. According to statistical data, we can see

³Statistical agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Electronic source: www.gender.stat.uz

that there are differences related to gender inequality in higher education organizations in 2018-2019 (Table 2).

The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan intends to expand the participation of women in the labor market, along with political measures aimed at improving the business environment for small businesses and private entrepreneurs, as well as household programs, as well as family entrepreneurship and crafts, socio-economic development of regions. programs, it is desirable to create new jobs through public works programs. The wide-ranging reforms implemented in our country to raise the value of women are of course of decisive importance as the legal frameworks in this regard have been created and are being regularly improved.

Conclusions and suggestions. The active participation of women in the future will ensure the increase of the national potential to maintain high rates of economic growth and increase the well-being of the entire population and women of Uzbekistan. The connection between the effective participation of women in the country's economy and the improvement of economic indicators is known to the whole world.

As a result of analyzing the activity of women in the labor market in our republic, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- In our republic, the level of economic activity of women has gradually increased in recent years;

- The distribution of women in the main sectors in Uzbekistan is around the world average, according to the World Bank, 26.9% in the agricultural sector, 17.4% in the industry % and 58.7% in the service sector;

- there are big differences in career choice of women and men. In most cases, women prefer social and humanitarian directions, such as healthcare, pedagogy and social services.

- the largest share of employed people corresponds to the lowest monthly wages in the economic activity sectors where women belong.

Recognizing the importance of the measures implemented to increase the economic activity of women in our republic in recent years, it is proposed to implement the following works in the future:

- taking measures to increase the employment rates of women in the IT sector, finance and insurance, and creating suitable jobs;

- consistently increasing the monthly wages in the fields where the majority of women are employed, that is, in the fields of education and healthcare;

- further expansion of opportunities for women, especially women in rural areas, to engage in entrepreneurial activities;

- in order to provide social protection and financial support to women on childcare leave, to restore the system of providing three-month allowances to unemployed mothers for childcare up to 2 years of age;

- it is desirable to facilitate the adjustment of women in the labor market after the child care leave up to 3 years of age, to create conditions for harmonizing education and family obligations.

To make a general conclusion, we should not forget that behind the achievements of every strong man lies the work and effort of a delicate woman. Women are creators of social material assets, human resources. Therefore, by creating the necessary conditions for women to get an education, to increase their educational privileges, to conduct research in the field of science and,

in general, to ensure their high position in society, men and it is necessary to ensure equal employment among women.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoev. SH.M. (2022) New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan. Completed second edition. - Tashkent: Publishing House of Uzbekistan, 416 pages.
2. Decree (2022) Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 28.01.2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". electronic source:<https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5841063>
3. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 22.07.2022 No. PQ-329 On additional measures to improve the system of vocational and entrepreneurship training for women” dated 22.07.2022 No. PQ-329
4. Hakim, C. (2004) Key Issues in Women's Work: Female Diversity and the Polarization of Women's Employment. London: Glass House Press.
5. Rakhmonova Aziza Tolibovna Tasks of Developing Women's Entrepreneurship Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, PhD supporting doctoral student AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies Volume 01, Issue 03, 2023 ISSN (E): XXX-XXX.
6. Rakhmonova Aziza Tolibovna THE ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR INCREASING THE EMPLOYMENT OF WOMEN Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service PhD supporting doctoral student ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 IMPACT FACTOR: 7.603 Vol 12, Issue 02, 2023
7. S Musayeva [MECHANISMS OF FUNCTIONING OF LOGISTIC STRUCTURES](#) Science and innovation 2 (A2), 196-202
8. S Musayeva [WAYS TO IMPROVE THE POLICY OF DISTRIBUTION OF GOODS IN FURNITURE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES](#) Science and innovation 2 (A2), 152-156
9. S Musayeva [IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN THE NEED TO EVALUATE ENTERPRISES](#) Science and innovation 2 (A2), 35-40
9. MS Azimovna [Ways to Improve the Use of Marketing Information in the Assessment of "Stekloplastik" LLC](#) American Journal of Economics and Business Management 5 (11), 338-343
10. MS Azimovna [Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT](#) Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities 12 (3), 93-97
11. Usmanov IA, Musayeva Sh.A. Features of marketing activities in the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS Journal NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 - 4230 VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1, Jan. -2021 <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/793>
12. Usmanov IA Musayeva Sh.A. Features of marketing organization in the market of construction services. Service. Scientific journal. - Samarkand. No. 2, 2021 - pp. 86-90.
13. Usmanov IA Study of the Provision of Construction Facilities with Management Personnel. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ORANGE TECHNOLOGY. Volume: 03 Issue: 9 | Sep 2021. p.31-33 <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/2171>
14. Usmanov IA, Jumanov Sh.N. Ways to improve quality control of construction and installation works. Oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences scientific

journal. ISSN 2181-1784. Volume 1, Issue 10. November 2021. – P. 651-658
<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-improve-quality-control-of-construction-and-installation-works>

15. Usmanov IA Buriev HT A development strategy for the construction industry in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation. International scientific and technical journal. Real estate: economy, administration. Moscow, MGSU-No. 4 / 2021
16. Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, RESEARCH OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF S SHARQ-UNIVERSAL-SMK LLC SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 6 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
17. Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna, EXAMINATION OF THE INVESTMENT PROJECT OF LEASING COMPANIES SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 7 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
18. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook "STAR-SEL" LLC publishing and creative department. Samarkand-2023